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A Creative Folio

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Where Healing Meets Learning

In halls where future nurses grew,
I stood with courage, steady, and true
When March brought silence to every street,
And fear made shadows at our feet.

A dean, a guardian of minds,
Of futures, fragile, undefined;
I held their hopes with careful hands,
As chaos swept across the lands.

But August called me to a place
Where chalk met masks on every face;
A rural district, far and wide,
Where mountains watched from either side.

The children waited, hearts unsure,
For learning's light to still endure;
And teachers worn by sleepless nights
Still fought for every child's right.

No stethoscope upon my chest,
Yet still I offered what I knew best
The nurse in me, though out of sight,
Guided every choice made in the night.

For healing lives in many forms,
In lessons taught, in shelters warm;
In guiding hands, in voices kind,
In hopes revived, in hearts aligned.

Two callings woven into one,
Two journeys shared beneath one sun
Where healing meets the will to teach,
Service finds its widest reach.

And though my path has changed its view,
The spirit of a nurse stays true
For once, you learn to care and lead,
You carry it in every deed.